

Changes in Immunoreactivity to Calcium-Binding Proteins in the Anterior Olfactory Nucleus of the Rat after Neonatal Olfactory Deprivation

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The effects of olfactory deprivation on the density of neuronal populations expressing the calcium-binding proteins calbindin D-28k, calretinin, and parvalbumin in the anterior olfactory nucleus of the rat were studied immunohistochemically in 60-day-old rats subjected to unilateral naris closure on the day of birth. The neuronal populations were characterized morphologically and topologically, and the density of each cell type was calculated in each subdivision of the anterior olfactory nucleus at seven rostrocaudal levels. Data were gathered into three groups: data from either the ipsilateral or contralateral anterior olfactory nucleus of experimental animals and data from control animals. Statistical analysis indicated that disruption of the normal afferent activity to one olfactory bulb affects the expression of the calcium-binding proteins investigated in the anterior olfactory nucleus, as revealed by variations in the density of certain neuronal populations. The observed effects were very heterogeneous and could not be related to any specific neuronal type, location, or to the expression of a given calcium-binding protein. Nevertheless, as a general rule the most affected neuronal populations were those expressing calbindin D-28k located in the rostral subdivisions. These subdivisions are the latest to develop in mammals and are those that receive the largest amount of inputs from the olfactory bulb.

Key Words: anterior olfactory nucleus; calcium-binding proteins; naris closure; olfactory system; postnatal development; quantitative neuroanatomy; sensory deprivation.

INTRODUCTION

In the olfactory pathway, the anterior olfactory nucleus (AON) is an important region in the processing of afferent sensory information after the first relay station in the main olfactory bulb (OB). The AON is located in the olfactory peduncle, caudal to the OB and rostral to the pyriform cortex. Histologically, the AON is a two-layer structure: an outer plexiform layer and a rather homogeneous inner cellular layer. Classically, these have been divided into five subdivisions, their boundaries established on the basis of their topological features (37). More recent studies have demonstrated that these topologically identified subdivisions display clearly different connectivity patterns (34, 59). The AON connects the OBs and secondary and tertiary olfactory centers (59) and is the first bilaterally innervated station of the olfactory pathway, thus enabling the cross-coordination of the olfactory information received from both OBs, and allowing similar information to arrive in both hemispheres (15, 16, 69). Reciprocally, the AON sends centrifugal projections to both OBs as well as a widespread projection to central olfactory

structures (50).

In biological systems, one of the regulating roles of calcium is to act as an intracellular second messenger (20, 28, 41, 44, 56, 63). In the nervous system, many cellular events are calcium-dependent, including receptor signal transduction and synaptic transmission.

To regulate cellular processes, the intracellular free calcium concentration is controlled through different mechanisms, including specific binding by cytoplasmic proteins; namely, calcium-binding proteins (CaBPs) (4, 14, 19, 20, 43). Calbindin D-28k (CB), calretinin (CR), and parvalbumin (PV) are CaBPs abundantly expressed in the nervous system (4, 66). Their localization in specific neurons has allowed further characterization

of neuronal populations across the brain, in some instances contributing to insight into their physiological roles (1, 4, 22, 66). In addition, study of their distribution in different sensory systems after experimental treatments aimed at modifying normal afferent activity has shown that the expression of CaBPs can be altered, pointing to the existence of regulatory mechanisms related to the afferent activity associated with full sensory experiences as well as with changes in intracellular calcium levels (18, 27, 54, 75, 77).

In the OB and the AON, immunohistochemistry for CaBPs has been successfully used to characterize specific nonoverlapping neuronal subpopulations within morphologically homogeneous groups of neurons (11– 13, 22, 32, 35, 36, 45, 58, 60). In this sensory system, the restriction of olfactory inputs produced by unilateral naris occlusion attenuates electrical activity in the OB (53) and produces a succession of anatomical, physiological and biochemical changes in the OB ipsilateral to the occluded naris (16). Among these changes, the expression of some CaBPs, including CB and PV, is reduced in several neuronal populations, suggesting that their expression is regulated by afferent activity (54).

Given these changes in the OB and the reciprocal synaptic relationships of this structure with the AON, changes affecting the OB as a consequence of sensory deprivation would also be expected to alter the normal physiological activity of the AON. In a previous stereological study we demonstrated an alteration in the postnatal development of the AON after neonatal deprivation, noted as a significant reduction in the size of both AONs in deprived animals as compared to controls (7). In the present work, the immunohistochemical localization of CB, CR, and PV in the rat AON was used to detect possible changes in these specific neuronal populations after olfactory deprivation. The initial aim was to describe the CB-, CR-, and PV-containing elements in the rat AON in order to obtain a full characterization of all neuronal types expressing these CaBPs. A further aim was to describe the effects of unilateral neonatal olfactory deprivation on the expression of these CaBPs, comparing the AONs ipsilateral and contralateral to the occluded naris with control structures. These data could provide some insight into the functions of these

proteins, the role of the neuronal populations containing them in olfactory processing, and as regards the plastic responses of the olfactory system to sensory deprivation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Timed pregnant female Wistar rats were housed singly under constant temperature conditions (22°C) on a 12/12 h light/dark cycle with food and water available ad libitum. Cages were checked daily to determine the date of birth, which was designated postnatal day 1 (P1).

On P1, half of the pups of each litter underwent unilateral naris closure by electrocauterization of the right external naris (deprived condition) as described elsewhere (7). In the remaining pups, electrocautery was performed just above the naris (control condition). The lesions were examined daily under a magnifying glass, and among the deprived animals those showing complete naris closure from P1 to P60 were selected. In all cases the experimental procedures conformed to NIH guidelines and were also in accordance with the guidelines of the European Community Council Directive (86/609/EEC) and current Spanish legislation for the use and care of laboratory animals (BOE 67/8509-12, 1988).

Eight unilaterally deprived Wistar rats (four males and four females) and an identical number of control animals of similar weight (230–250 g) were perfused when they reached P60. Briefly, the animals deeply anesthetized by an intramuscular injection of a mixture of ketamine hydrochloride (Ketolar, Parke-Davis, Barcelona, Spain) and tiacine hydrochloride (Rompun, Bayer, Leverkusen, Germany), (3/4) 1 ml/kg body weight. They were perfused intracardially with 100 ml of Ringer's solution followed by 400 ml of a fixative solution made up of 4% (w/v) paraformaldehyde and 0.2% (w/v) picric acid in 0.1 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.3 (PB). The brains were removed and tissue blocks containing

both the OBs and the AONs were dissected out using a rodent brain matrix. These blocks were postfixed in the same fixative solution at 4°C for an additional two hours and then cryoprotected by immersion in 30% sucrose in PB at 4°C until they sank. Six series

of coronal sections were cut at 30-um thickness using a cryostat (Leica Jung, Nussloch, Germany) and were collected free-floating in PB. From each tissue block of both OBs and AONs, one series was Nissl-stained with 0.25% thionin for analysis of the general histological organization. The remaining series were used for immunohistochemical studies.

Immunohistochemistry

A reduced expression of tyrosine hydroxylase (TH) in the OB ipsilateral to the closed naris has been described as an indicator of the effectiveness of naris occlusion (5, 6, 26). Thus, one series from each OB from both the deprived and control animals was processed for the immunohistochemical detection of

TH. After correct deprivation has been confirmed with this analysis, series from each AON were processed for the immunohistochemical detection of the CaBPs under analysis, i.e., CB, CR, and PV. In all cases, immunohistochemical detection of the different markers was performed following the avidinbiotin immunoperoxidase method (38). Free-floating sections were washed in PB and incubated for 30 min in 0.05% Triton X-100 and either 10% normal horse serum or 10% normal goat serum in PB. After a wash in PB, sections of the OB were incubated for 48 h at 4°C in 1:10,000 mouse anti-TH (KTHM788, Incstar Corp., Stillwater, Minnesota), and sections from different series of the AON were incubated in the following solutions: 1:5,000 mouse anti-CB (clone 300) (24), 1:5,000 rabbit anti-CB (Swant antibodies, Bellinzona, Switzerland), 1:15,000 rabbit anti-CR (65), 1:5,000 mouse anti-PV (clone 235) (23), 1:5,000 rabbit anti-PV (Swant antibodies, Bellinzona, Switzerland), diluted in 0.05% Triton X-100 in PB. After washes in PB (3 x 10 min), sections were transferred for 2 h at room temperature to a medium containing biotinylated anti-mouse or anti-rabbit immunoglobulins (Vector, Burlingame, CA) diluted 1:250 in PB. After several rinses in PB (3 x 10 min), sections were incubated for 1 h at room temperature in Vectastain Elite ABC reagent (Vector) diluted 1:200 in PB. Tissue-bound peroxidase was visualized using 0.03% 3,3'-diaminobenzidine tetrahydrochloride (Sigma Chemicals, St. Louis, MO) and 0.003% hydrogen peroxide in 0.2 M Tris-HCl buffer, pH 7.6, for 10–15 min until the desired staining intensity was reached. Sections were mounted on gelatincoated slides, air-dried, dehydrated through a graded ethanol series, cleared with xylene, and coverslipped with Entellan (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany).

The primary antibodies have been fully characterized elsewhere: mouse anti-TH (KTHM788, Incstar Corp.); mouse anti-CB (24); mouse anti-PV (23); rabbit anti-CR; (65); rabbit anti-CB and anti-PV (Swant antibodies, Bellinzona, Switzerland). Controls of the specificity of the immunostaining were performed omitting either the primary or the secondary antibodies, both separately and together. No residual reaction was observed.

Analysis

Analysis of the changes occurring in the immunoreactivity to the CaBPs studied was performed on seven levels (L1–L7) defined through the rostro-caudal axis of the AON that were representative of the whole extent of this structure and comparable among the animals. Each of these seven levels was defined on the basis of its anatomical and morphological features, as described elsewhere (7). The sections matching these selected levels, as well as the immediate anterior and posterior sections of the same series, were digitized on a photomicroscope (Olympus AX-70) with a digital camera (Apogee Instruments, Tucson, AZ) connected to a computer with the appropriate software (Adobe Photoshop 5.5., Adobe Systems Inc., San Jose, CA). In each section, the boundaries of the AON and of its subdivisions present

at that level were plotted and their areas were measured using NIH Image software. After identification of the different cellular types according to their morphological features and CaBP expression (see Results below), the immunopositive cell profiles of each type were counted and their mean density was calculated and expressed as the number of cell profiles per 10,000 μm^2 .

The data obtained were gathered in three groups: two experimental groups from the deprived animals (AON ipsilateral and contralateral to the closed naris) and an additional group comprising the AONs of control animals. To minimize errors in the detection of significant differences between groups, statistical analysis was performed using non-parametric tests. Depending on the type of sample for comparisons, and since both samples were considered matched groups, the Wilcoxon rank test for paired data was used to compare data from both experimental AONs (ipsilateral vs contralateral). The statistical analysis used to compare the data from either of the experimental AONs with the control AONs, which were considered independent populations, was performed using the Mann–Whitney U test. For all tests, values of $P < 0.01$ were considered as highly significant, and $0.01 < P < 0.05$ was considered as significant for the differences.

RESULTS

General Features of CaBP-Immunolabeling in the Control AON

We followed the nomenclature proposed by Haberly and Price (34), according to which the AON is divided into five subdivisions: external (AONe), lateral (AONl), dorsal (AONd), medial (AONm), and ventroposterior (AONvp). Despite this nomenclature being relatively constant among authors, the cytoarchitectonic homogeneity of these subdivisions made it difficult to pinpoint their exact their boundaries. Since the present study required homogeneous criteria for the location of the exact boundaries of each subdivision in the different animals, we used anatomical landmarks as a reference in order to precisely define such boundaries. These criteria have been described previously (7) and allow a reasonably homogeneous morphological comparison among different animals.

Immunolabeling for CB, CR, and PV revealed the presence of immunopositive cell profiles located in all the subdivisions of the AON and distributed throughout its whole rostrocaudal extension. The morphological features of the immunostained elements allowed us to identify six different neuronal types. Three of them were identified in the subdivisions forming the AON ring (AONl, AONm, AONd, and AONvp), while the other three types were found only in the AONe.

Neuronal types of the ring subdivisions. CaBP-immunostained neuronal types located in the ring subdivisions were mainly distributed throughout the inner half of the cellular layer. On the basis of their somatic morphology, they were designated large pyramidal

cells, fusiform cells and polymorphic cells. After immunohistochemistry for all the markers investigated, specific populations belonging to each of these neuronal types were detected.

Large pyramidal cells (Fig. 1a). These had pyramidal or triangular cell bodies, maximum diameters ranging from 21 to 25 μm . One main dendritic trunk arose from each vertex and these were oriented radially with the apical dendrite directed towards superficial regions, and the other two or three basal dendrites were directed towards the inner regions.

Fusiform cells (Fig. 1b). These had ovoid or fusiform cell bodies, the major axis ranging from 15 to 20 μm in length. They displayed at least two main dendritic trunks arising from opposite poles of the soma and extending in opposite directions. Neurons located in the inner region of the cell layer had their dendrites oriented radially to the AON layering, whereas those in the outer region had their dendrites parallel to the layering.

Polymorphic cells (Fig. 1c). These cells had highly variable somatic morphologies. The major axis ranged from 12 to 22 μm in length. They were multipolar cells, both the number and orientation of their dendrites varying considerably.

Neuronal types of the AONE. Three additional neuronal types were found only in the AONE. These were arranged in rows parallel to the surface, each neuronal type at a different level, conferring the AONE a laminated appearance. We typified these cells as granule cells, medium-sized pyramidal cells, and pyriform cells.

Granule cells (Fig. 1d). These cells were found at the outer edge of the AONE, forming a narrow cellular layer within the Ia plexiform sublayer. Their somatic morphological features were similar to those of the granule cells of the OB, with small (7.5–9 μm) round or oval cell bodies from which short, winding and varicose dendrites arose. These dendrites were oriented perpendicular to the superficial region, where they branched. Occasionally, a basal thin axon-like prolongation was observed. Neurons with identical morphological features were detected after immunostaining for all the CaBPs investigated.

The other two cell types observed in the AONE—medium-sized pyramidal cells and pyriform cells—were only detected after CB-immunostaining. Both neuronal types were distributed within the Ib plexiform sublayer and, in both cases, their staining intensity was lower than that of granule cells.

Medium-sized pyramidal cells (Fig. 1e). These displayed similar morphological features to the pyramidal cells of the ring subdivisions but the size of their bodies was smaller (15–19 μm). In addition, they showed a weak immunostaining restricted to the soma and proximal region of the primary processes (normally three), which showed a radial orientation.

Pyriform cells (Fig. 1f). These showed a medium labeling intensity. They clearly had pyriform cell bodies (9–12 μm maximum diameter) with one primary dendrite oriented toward the outer region of the AONE.

Control of Olfactory Deprivation

Nissl-stained sections of the OBs ipsilateral to the occluded naris revealed a remarkable size reduction in comparison with the contralateral one. Moreover, the ipsilateral OB had a reduced number of TH-immunopositive juxtglomerular cells (Fig. 2). These effects are the most typical features occurring in the OB as a consequence of deprivation (5, 6, 26). On the basis of these findings, we were able to confirm that all the experimental animals used in the present study had been correctly deprived and that the sham-operated animals had not been affected by the maneuver.

Effects of Deprivation on Immunoreactivity to CaBPs

The data reported here were obtained from direct counting of immunoreactive cell profiles and measurements of the area of the AON subdivision in which they appeared. However, it is necessary to take into account that, at some levels, the dimensions of several AON subdivisions are also affected by deprivation (7). In short, in most cases the area of the subdivisions of the experimental AONs showed a reduction in size as compared with the same regions of the AON from the control animals. This decrease was more marked in the ipsilateral than in the contralateral AON of the deprived animals. Since such a size reduction could have affected the data obtained, the density of the immunostained cell profiles was calculated in two ways: one, taking as a reference the true measured areas of the subdivisions under study (represented on the graphs) and, two, using as a reference area the mean area of each AON subdivision from the control animals. In both cases, the statistical analysis demonstrated the existence of significant differences in the same cell populations, although in some cases the degree of statistical significance differed. These findings clearly suggest that a real change in cell density takes place, regardless of the reduction in AON size.

After detailed analysis and comparison of the three experimental groups—ipsilateral AON of deprived animals, contralateral AON of deprived animals, and control animals—we found evident modifications in the density of the immunoreactive cell profiles (data are plotted graphically in Figs. 3, 5, 7, 8, 9, and 13 and in Tables 1–10).

Ring subdivisions. Large pyramidal cells and fusiform cells were immunoreactive for both CB and PV in all the ring subdivisions. Despite this, in some subdivisions these populations were too scarce to be analyzed statistically. For this reason we only analyzed the CB-immunostained populations of both cell types in the AONl and the AONd, where they were relatively abundant. In both subdivisions, the density of CB-positive large pyramidal cells and fusiform cells increased at practically all levels in the experimental AONs as compared to the controls (Figs. 3 and 4; Tables 1, 2). The density of large pyramidal cells was very significantly increased in the ipsilateral AONl and the AONd in comparison with the controls (Fig. 3; Table 1), whereas the density of fusiform cells increased in the AONl and in the AONd of

both hemispheres of the experimental animals (Fig. 3; Table 2). In addition to the increased cell density of both neuronal types in the experimental animals, there was a consistent increase in the staining of these cells, their whole dendritic arborization being labeled in the experimental animals, whereas in control sections incubated together, only the initial portions of the primary dendrites were stained (Fig. 4).

The polymorphic cells were positive for all the three CaBPs studied and appeared in all the ring subdivisions. The density of polymorphic cells expressing CB pointed to a significant increase in the AONm of both the ipsilateral and the contralateral sides of the experimental animals as compared to the controls, whereas in the remaining subdivisions no significant differences were detected (Figs. 5 and 6a–d; Table 3). By contrast, the CR-labeled polymorphic cells showed a decreased density in both the AONm of the experimental animals at the medium and caudal levels (L6 and L7). This decrease was highly significant in the ipsilateral hemisphere and in L6 of the contralateral AONm, whereas it was only significant in L7 of the contralateral AONm (Figs. 6e, 6f, and 7; Table 4). In the remaining subdivisions of the ring, no differences were found except in the AONd in L4, where a significant reduction was detected in both hemispheres of the experimental animals (Fig. 7; Table 4).

Concerning the PV-positive polymorphic cells, a statistically significant increase was detected in most levels of both the AONI and AONd of the experimental animals as compared to the controls (Fig. 8; Table 5). However, whereas in the AONd the increase was greater on the ipsilateral side, in the AONI major significant differences were detected on the side contralateral to the deprived naris (Fig. 8; Table 5).

AONe. Granule cells were strongly labeled for all the CaBPs investigated but appeared only in the AONe. The effect of deprivation on this population was striking since within this morphologically homogeneous cell type each chemically identified subgroup showed a different response. Thus, CB-positive granule cells showed a significant increase in the three rostral-most levels (highly significant in the L1) of the ipsilateral AONe (Figs. 9, 10; Table 6). Regarding granule cells expressing CR, these showed an increase in their density at all rostro-caudal levels and in both the ipsilateral and contralateral AONe (Figs. 9, 11; Table 7). This change was highly significant in L4. By contrast, with regard to PV-labeling, the density of granule cells expressing this marker was significantly reduced in the AONe ipsilateral to the occluded naris only in the rostralmost levels (L1 and L2) (Figs. 9, 12; Table 8).

Medium-sized pyramidal neurons and pyriform neurons constituted neuronal subpopulations that also appeared only in the AONe, but were only detected after CB-immunostaining. Regarding the former, these showed a highly significant reduction in both AONs of the experimental animals in levels L2, L3 and L4 (Figs. 13, 14a, and 14b; Table 9). By contrast, in the case of pyriform neurons, the density was similar in all three

groups in the rostral-most levels (L1–L2–L3), whereas their density was very significantly increased on both sides of the experimental animals in the caudal-most level (L4) (Figs. 13, 14c–f; Table 10).

In sum, the results obtained can be summarized as follows: (i) olfactory deprivation induces changes in the density of immunostained cell profiles in both AONs of experimental animals. These differences are larger in the ipsilateral AON than the contralateral one. (ii) Among the different neuronal subpopulations, those expressing the CaBPs investigated in the AONvp seemed to be unaffected by the maneuver. (iii) The modifications in cell density did not follow a common pattern. An increased density was observed in some cell populations, whereas in other cases density decreased with respect to control values. (iv) The nature of these variations in cell density was not related either to the CaBP expressed or its localization in the AON (i.e., increases and decreases were observed in the same subdivision or in the different neuronal populations expressing the same CaBP).

DISCUSSION

Here we have analyzed the effects that unilateral neonatal olfactory deprivation exert on the neuronal populations expressing CB, CR, or PV in the adult rat AON. Our results demonstrate that early olfactory deprivation induces changes in the density of some of these neuronal populations in both the AON ipsilateral to the occluded naris and, although to a lesser extent, in the contralateral one. In this respect, previous neurochemical and neuroanatomical studies have shown that after unilateral olfactory deprivation the OB contralateral to the occluded naris is not affected, and is in fact indistinguishable from those of control animals (17). Thus, in those studies, the contralateral OB was used as a control (6, 16, 26). By contrast, in the case of the AON, our previous research had shown that after neonatal olfactory deprivation, the size of some subdivisions of both AONs undergo a significant reduction as compared to controls (7). In addition, the present research demonstrates that both AONs are also affected as regards the expression of the CaBPs studied. Therefore, in this type of study, the contralateral AON is not a control structure and cannot be used as a reference to compare the effects occurring the ipsilateral side. This different effect of sensory deprivation on both olfactory structures—the OB and the AON—can be explained in terms of the notion that the OBs receive afferent information in an ipsilateral and separate way whereas the information reaching each AON comes from both OBs (69, 70). Nevertheless, although olfactory information can reach the AON ipsilateral to the deprived side via the contralateral OB following deprivation (69), this processing pathway is dissimilar to normal conditions because the activity of the direct pathway (ipsilateral OB-ipsilateral AON) is eliminated. Finally, it is interesting to note that, theoretically, the contralateral OB can be affected since this structure receives centrifugal inputs from

the contralateral AON that is altered by deprivation, as we demonstrate here. However, as indicated above, no changes were detected in the contralateral OB.

The features and degree of modification of the neuronal populations studied vary, depending on the AON subdivisions, the neuronal population, and the CaBP expressed. This heterogeneous response of the expression of CaBPs after deprivation has also been reported in other sensory systems, such reports demonstrating that changes in the expression of CB, CR and PV are different, and frequently opposite, depending on the system manipulated and on the structure examined within the system in question (2, 10, 18, 25, 33, 49, 57, 62, 64, 73). As examples, the expression of CB and PV decreases in the OB after unilateral olfactory deprivation (54), in the peripheral nervous system after denervation (52, 61), and in the striate cortex after monocular deprivation (10, 25). Similarly, the expression of CR is reduced in the ventral cochlear nucleus after either cochlear ablation (75) or auditory deprivation (18). By contrast, an increase occurs, for example, in the expression of PV in the superior colliculus after retinal deafferentation (47) or in the expression of CB and PV in the medial trapezoid nucleus after auditory deprivation (18). Finally, CaBP expression may remain stable after these experimental approaches, as occurs with the expression of CR in the nucleus magnocellularis after bilateral cochlea removal (72). All these studies therefore demonstrate that modification of sensory inputs induces changes in the level of CB, CR, and PV, although the heterogeneity of the response indicates that there is no unique mechanism regulating their expression but that intrinsic properties of the cell population expressing them, such as the origin and/or connection patterns, could determine such a response.

Several methodological aspects may influence the modifications to the immunohistochemical detection of CaBPs in these experimental approaches. Changes producing a masking or unmasking of epitopes, variations in the intracellular redistribution of the proteins, or modifications in their turnover could account for the observed differences in their immunohistochemical detection (18). The conformational status of CaBPs depends on their calcium-binding status and, at high calcium concentrations, CaBPs display a calcium-binding conformation that is preferentially recognized by antibodies (76). Since the changes that follow deprivation may account for alterations in intracellular calcium levels, the changes in immunoreactivity for CaBPs that follow deprivation could be due, at least in part, to conformational changes related to modifications in the intracellular calcium concentration. Nevertheless, the coincidence of such changes with alterations in the morphology and physiology of olfactory centers after deprivation strongly suggest that modifications in calcium levels also affect the mechanisms regulating CaBP expression (27, 28, 54, 56).

One of the most important factors in the control of the CaBP expression is the activity of afferent fibers, presynaptic activity being the common regulatory signal (2, 10, 18, 25, 49, 54, 57, 62, 73). Neurotransmitter release, especially the excitatory release of amino acids, modulates the expression of

certain proteins such as CB (9, 39). In the OB, the release of glutamate by the olfactory receptor terminals regulates the expression of TH (55). Concerning CaBPs, some data suggest that the relationship between the level of glutamatergic activity and the modifications of their expression is direct (18, 31, 40, 62). The glutamate-mediated activation of calcium channels increases intracellular calcium levels (54, 71), which induces an upregulation of the calcium buffering systems. In this sense, it has been demonstrated that CB levels increase in response to a rise in glutamatergic transmission (31, 40). In the opposite situation, a decrease in CR expression in the vestibular nuclei as a result of a reduced glutamatergic transmission has been detected following the loss of labyrinthine inputs (62). In addition, the level of glutamate release has also been correlated with alterations in the expression pattern of CB, CR and PV following afferent input loss in the auditory (18) and olfactory systems (54, 74).

The relay neurons of the OB projecting to the AON— i.e., mitral and tufted cells—use glutamate as a neurotransmitter (36, 48). The electrical attenuation of these neurons that follows naris closure (54) should give rise to a reduced glutamate release onto their target cells in the AON. According to the above works on other systems, this would induce a down-regulation of CaBP expression. This is consistent with our results concerning the large reduction in the density of CaBP-immunopositive neuronal populations in the AONe, the subdivision that receives the largest amount of inputs from the OB. The reduction in CaBP expression in this subdivision is dramatic in the case of medium-sized pyriform cells, which are CB-immunopositive, and, according to their location, are the main cell population receiving direct inputs from mitral/tufted cells (70). Therefore, it could be speculated that the decrease in the CB-immunoreactivity in these cells would be a consequence of an attenuation of glutamatergic activity as a result of the loss of afferent stimuli and that the maintenance of stable levels of CB in medium-sized pyramidal cells would require a normal complement of inputs.

As observed here, the densities of other neuronal populations such as pyramidal cells and fusiform cells in the AONl and the AONd, and pyriform cells and granule-like cells in the AONe, all of them positive for CB, underwent an increase in the experimental animals. This increased expression of CaBPs seems difficult to reconcile with the fact that, given the attenuation in the electrical activity of the system, the most frequent reaction to deprivation is the down-regulation of CaBP expression. However, increased expression of CaBPs after sensory deprivation has been also reported in the auditory and visual systems (18, 47). Increased CaBP expression may confer a certain stability and resilience to activity-dependent alterations after the disruption of the sensory input. Some experimental models suggest that deprivation in sensory systems induces apoptosis and neuronal death (21, 30). The increase in the buffering capacity, by increasing CaBP expression, of cells affected by loss of sensory inputs may be one of the mechanisms promoted for their survival (18, 46). Additionally, the increased density of some neuronal populations can be explained in terms of a response to increased activity subsequent to a down-regulation of inhibition.

Inhibitory neurons located presynaptically to these populations could lose their activity after deprivation, thus enabling increased activity in postsynaptic targets, in turn resulting in increased CaBP expression. The expression and activity of some proteins are developmentally regulated and input-dependent (42, 67, 68). In most sensory systems, the blockade of sensory input has the greatest effects developmentally, during the so-called “critical period,” when sensory functions are most susceptible to environmental influences (51). In the visual system, for example, sensory input during the early postnatal period is essential for the development and maintenance of protein kinase C in the visual cortex (29). Concerning CaBPs, a transient expression has been observed during development, their distribution being modified until adulthood when expression reaches its definitive pattern (1). In the AON, the distribution pattern of neurons expressing CB varies considerably during the development in both quantitative and qualitative ways. The number of CB-positive cells increases from P10 to P20, whereas there is a substantial reduction in this cell population from P20 to P30 (3). By contrast, CR appears earlier in all regions of the brain, including the AON (1, 8) and indeed is present at birth (1). It is conceivable that deprivation during the critical period might affect CaBPs whose expression is more precocious and constant during this period to a lesser extent, their expression being less sensitive to attenuation of the electrical activity following naris closure. This is in agreement with our findings, in which the expression pattern of CB, whose appearance is postnatal, is the one most affected by deprivation, whereas only slight changes were observed concerning CR immunoreactivity.

In sum, unilateral olfactory deprivation performed neonatally leads to modifications in the density of certain neuronal populations expressing the CaBPs investigated in the AON. Among the affected neuronal populations, most of them are characterized by the expression of CB. In addition, given the developmental gradient of the AON, most of these populations are located in the AONe, a subdivision that receives the bulk of projections from the OB and that is the most immature region at birth. These results demonstrate the presence of regulatory mechanisms in the expression of the CaBPs investigated in certain neuronal populations of the rat AON. Given the distinct sign of such modifications among neuronal types, the factors able to alter the expression of these proteins may be of different nature. Among them, the large reduction in the number of CB-immunopositive medium-sized pyramidal cells in both the ipsilateral and the contralateral AONe suggests that one of the most important factors involved in the regulation of CB expression after naris closure is the attenuation of glutamatergic inputs from mitral and tufted cells.

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FIGURES

FIG. 1. CaBP-immunopositive neuronal types in the AON. Scale bar, 50 μ m. (a) Large pyramidal cell CB-immunopositive in the AONL. (b) Fusiform cell positive to PV in the AONm. (c) Polymorphic cells labeled for CR in the AONL. (d) Granule-like cells (arrowheads) immunoreactive to CB in the AONe. (e) Medium-sized pyramidal cells (arrowheads) positive to CB in the AONe. (f) CB-immunoreactive pyriform cells (arrowheads) in the AONe.

FIG. 2. Tyrosine hydroxylase-immunostaining in the glomerular layer of the olfactory bulb. Scale bar, 125 μ m. (a) Bulb contralateral to the occluded naris. (b) Bulb ipsilateral to the occluded naris.

FIG. 3. Mean density \pm SEM of large pyramidal cells and fusiform cells immunoreactive for calbindin D-28k in the AONI and the AONd of each level where these subdivisions appeared. Symbols (i.e., * and #) indicate significant statistical differences between either the ipsilateral or the contralateral AON of deprived animals as compared to controls using the Mann–Whitney U test. See Tables 1 and 2 for more details. *Significant differences ($0.01 < P \leq 0.05$); #highly significant differences ($P < 0.01$).

CB-immunopositive Large pyramidal cells

CB-immunopositive Fusiform cells

FIG. 4. Calbindin D-28k-immunostaining in coronal sections of the AON in control animal (left panels) and in the AON ipsilateral to the occluded naris of an experimental animal (right panels). Asterisks indicate the anterior component of the anterior commissure. Scale bar, 500 μ m for a, b; 200 μ m for c, d; 100 μ m for e, f. (a, b) Overview of the AON showing the density of CB-immunostained large pyramidal and fusiform cells in a control AON (a) and in the AON ipsilateral to the occluded naris (b). Dashed line indicates the boundary between the AONI and the AONd. (c, d) High magnification photomicrographs of the AONI showing the number of large pyramidal and fusiform cells immunostained for calbindin D-28k in a control AON (c) and in the AON ipsilateral to the occluded naris (d). (e, f) Detail of neurons shown in c and d showing the differences in the staining of the dendritic arborization of immunostained cells in control (e) and in the hemisphere of deprived experimental animals (f).

FIG. 5. Mean density \pm SEM of calbindin D-28k-immunopositive polymorphic cells in the ring subdivisions at each level where these subdivisions appeared. Symbols (i.e., * and #) indicate statistically significant differences between either the ipsilateral or the contralateral AON of deprived animals as compared to controls. See Table 3 for more details. *Significant differences ($0.01 < P < 0.05$).

CB-immunopositive Polymorphic cells

FIG. 6. Polymorphic cells in the AONm and in the AONvp after CaBP-immunostaining. Asterisks indicate the anterior component of the anterior commissure. Scale bar, 500 μ m for a, b; 200 μ m for c–f. (a, b) CB-immunostaining in the AONm and the AONvp from a control animal (a) and the AON ipsilateral to the occluded bulb of an experimental animal (b). Dashed line indicates the boundary between the AONm and the AONvp. (c, d) High magnification photomicrographs showing CB-positive polymorphic cells in the AONm in a control (c) and in an experimental animal (d). (e, f) CR-immunopositive polymorphic cells in the AONm of a control (e) and in an experimental animal (f).

FIG. 7. Mean density \pm SEM of CR-immunopositive polymorphic cells in the ring subdivisions in each level where these subdivisions appeared. Symbols (i.e., * and #) indicate statistically significant differences between either the ipsilateral or the contralateral AON of deprived animals as compared to controls. See Table 4 for more details. *Significant differences ($0.01 < P < 0.05$); #highly significant differences ($P < 0.01$).

CR-immunopositive Polymorphic cells

FIG. 8. Mean density \pm SEM of PV-immunopositive polymorphic cells in the ring subdivisions at each level where these subdivisions appeared. Symbols (i.e., * and #) indicate statistically significant differences between either the ipsilateral or the contralateral AON of deprived animals as compared to controls. See Table 5 for more details. *Significant differences ($0.01 < P < 0.05$).

PV-immunopositive Polymorphic cells

FIG. 9. Mean density \pm SEM of calbindin D-28k-, calretinin-, and parvalbumin-immunoreactive granule cells in the AONe. Symbols (i.e., * and #) indicate statistically significant differences between either the ipsilateral or the contralateral AON of deprived animals as compared to controls. See Tables 6–8 for more details. *Significant differences ($0.01 < P < 0.05$); #highly significant differences ($P < 0.01$).

TABLE 1

CB-Immunopositive Large Pyramidal Cells			
AON subdivision	Level	Ipsilateral vs control	Contralateral vs control
AONI	1	$U = 2.0; P = 0.0016^*$	$U = 15.0; P = 0.0742$
	2	$U = 12.5; P = 0.0406^{**}$	$U = 17.0; P = 0.1152$
	3	$U = 1.0; P = 0.0011^*$	$U = 15.0; P = 0.0742$
	4	$U = 6.5; P = 0.0074^*$	$U = 16.0; P = 0.0929$
	5	$U = 1.0; P = 0.0011^*$	$U = 16.5; P = 0.1036$
	6	$U = 6.0; P = 0.0063^*$	$U = 23.0; P = 0.3446$
AONd	3	$U = 7.0; P = 0.0087^*$	$U = 6.0; P = 0.0063^*$
	4	$U = 5.0; P = 0.0046^*$	$U = 14.0; P = 0.0587$
	5	$U = 3.0; P = 0.0023^*$	$U = 13.5; P = 0.0520$
	6	$U = 18.5; P = 0.1563$	$U = 19.5; P = 0.1893$

Note. Statistical values for U and P obtained from the Mann–Whitney U test for the CB-immunopositive large pyramidal cells in the AONI and the AONd. ******Significant statistical differences ($0.01 < P < 0.05$). *****Highly significant statistical differences ($P < 0.01$).

TABLE 2

CB-Immunopositive Fusiform Cells			
AON subdivision	Level	Ipsilateral vs control	Contralateral vs control
AONI	1	$U = 23.5; P = 0.3720$	$U = 9.5; P = 0.0181^{**}$
	2	$U = 6.0; P = 0.0063^*$	$U = 7.0; P = 0.0087^*$
	3	$U = 11.0; P = 0.0274^{**}$	$U = 5.5; P = 0.0054^*$
	4	$U = 12.5; P = 0.0406^{**}$	$U = 12.0; P = 0.0357^{**}$
	5	$U = 11.5; P = 0.0313^{**}$	$U = 11.5; P = 0.0313^{**}$
	6	$U = 12.0; P = 0.0357^{**}$	$U = 7.0; P = 0.0087^*$
AONd	3	$U = 1.0; P = 0.0011^*$	$U = 0.0; P = 0.0008^*$
	4	$U = 0.0; P = 0.0008^*$	$U = 5.5; P = 0.0054^*$
	5	$U = 0.0; P = 0.0008^*$	$U = 4.0; P = 0.0033^*$
	6	$U = 1.0; P = 0.0011^*$	$U = 1.5; P = 0.0014^*$

Note. Statistical values for U and P obtained from the Mann–Whitney U test for the CB-immunopositive fusiform cells in the AONI and the AONd. ******Significant statistical differences ($0.01 < P < 0.05$). *****Highly significant statistical differences ($P < 0.01$).

TABLE 3

CB-Immunopositive Polymorphic Cells			
AON subdivision	Level	Ipsilateral vs control	Contralateral vs control
AONI	1	$U = 23.0; P = 0.3446$	$U = 31.0; P = 0.9164$
	2	$U = 28.0; P = 0.6744$	$U = 28.0; P = 0.6744$
	3	$U = 16.0; P = 0.0929$	$U = 24.0; P = 0.4008$
	4	$U = 14.5; P = 0.0661$	$U = 30.0; P = 0.8336$
	5	$U = 16.0; P = 0.0929$	$U = 24.5; P = 0.4309$
	6	$U = 31.0; P = 0.9164$	$U = 19.0; P = 0.1722$
AONd	3	$U = 20.0; P = 0.2076$	$U = 14.0; P = 0.0587$
	4	$U = 18.0; P = 0.1415$	$U = 23.0; P = 0.3446$
	5	$U = 27.0; P = 0.5995$	$U = 25.5; P = 0.4948$
	6	$U = 24.0; P = 0.4008$	$U = 29.0; P = 0.7527$
AONm	5	$U = 8.0; P = 0.0117^*$	$U = 13.0; P = 0.0460^*$
	6	$U = 13.0; P = 0.0460^*$	$U = 12.5; P = 0.0406^*$
AONvp	7	$U = 10.0; P = 0.0209^*$	$U = 15.0; P = 0.0742$
	5	$U = 23.5; P = 0.3720$	$U = 16.0; P = 0.0929$
	6	$U = 21.5; P = 0.2701$	$U = 23.0; P = 0.3446$
	7	$U = 16.0; P = 0.0929$	$U = 31.0; P = 0.9164$

Note. Statistical values for U and P obtained from the Mann–Whitney U test for the CB-immunopositive polymorphic cells in the ring subdivisions, AONI, AONd, AONm, and AONvp. *Significant statistical differences ($0.01 < P < 0.05$).

TABLE 4

CR-Immunopositive Polymorphic Cells			
AON subdivision	Level	Ipsilateral vs control	Contralateral vs control
AONI	1	$U = 29.0; P = 0.7527$	$U = 29.0; P = 0.7527$
	2	$U = 23.0; P = 0.3446$	$U = 28.0; P = 0.6744$
	3	$U = 22.0; P = 0.2936$	$U = 29.0; P = 0.7527$
	4	$U = 23.5; P = 0.3720$	$U = 29.0; P = 0.7527$
	5	$U = 22.5; P = 0.3184$	$U = 28.0; P = 0.6744$
	6	$U = 21.0; P = 0.2480$	$U = 20.0; P = 0.2076$
AONd	3	$U = 25.5; P = 0.4948$	$U = 18.5; P = 0.1563$
	4	$U = 11.5; P = 0.0313$	$U = 10.0; P = 0.0209$
	5	$U = 25.5; P = 0.4948$	$U = 25.0; P = 0.4622$
AONm	6	$U = 25.5; P = 0.4948$	$U = 24.5; P = 0.4309$
	5	$U = 19.0; P = 0.1722$	$U = 20.0; P = 0.2076$
	6	$U = 7.0; P = 0.0087^*$	$U = 7.0; P = 0.0087^*$
AONvp	7	$U = 7.0; P = 0.0087^*$	$U = 10.5; P = 0.0239^{**}$
	5	$U = 19.5; P = 0.1893$	$U = 20.0; P = 0.2076$
	6	$U = 24.5; P = 0.4309$	$U = 28.5; P = 0.7132$
	7	$U = 28.0; P = 0.6744$	$U = 30.5; P = 0.8748$

Note. Statistical values for U and P obtained from the Mann–Whitney U test for the CR-immunopositive polymorphic cells in the ring subdivisions, AONI, AONd, AONm, and AONvp. **Significant statistical differences ($0.01 < P < 0.05$). *Highly significant statistical differences ($P < 0.01$).

TABLE 5

PV-Immunopositive Polymorphic Cells			
AON subdivision	Level	Ipsilateral vs control	Contralateral vs control
AONI	1	$U = 20.0; P = 0.2076$	$U = 13.0; P = 0.0460^*$
	2	$U = 26.0; P = 0.5286$	$U = 12.5; P = 0.0406^*$
	3	$U = 11.5; P = 0.0313^*$	$U = 13.0; P = 0.0460^*$
	4	$U = 22.0; P = 0.2936$	$U = 21.0; P = 0.2480$
	5	$U = 27.5; P = 0.6365$	$U = 12.0; P = 0.0357^*$
	6	$U = 13.0; P = 0.0460^*$	$U = 11.5; P = 0.0313^*$
AONd	3	$U = 11.0; P = 0.0274^*$	$U = 10.0; P = 0.0209^*$
	4	$U = 28.0; P = 0.6744$	$U = 27.0; P = 0.5995$
	5	$U = 12.0; P = 0.0357^*$	$U = 22.0; P = 0.2936$
AONm	6	$U = 11.0; P = 0.0274^*$	$U = 10.5; P = 0.0239^*$
	5	$U = 24.0; P = 0.4008$	$U = 25.0; P = 0.4622$
	6	$U = 23.0; P = 0.3446$	$U = 19.0; P = 0.1722$
AONvp	7	$U = 24.0; P = 0.4008$	$U = 28.0; P = 0.6744$
	5	$U = 22.0; P = 0.2936$	$U = 30.0; P = 0.8336$
	6	$U = 24.0; P = 0.4008$	$U = 26.0; P = 0.5286$
	7	$U = 25.0; P = 0.4622$	$U = 26.0; P = 0.5286$

Note. Statistical values for U and P obtained from the Mann–Whitney U test for the PV-immunopositive polymorphic cells in the ring subdivisions, AONI, AONd, AONm, and AONvp. *Significant statistical differences ($0.01 < P < 0.05$).